

THE USE OF BLACK TEA WASTE AS A THERMO-OXIDATION STABILIZER FOR POLYETHYLENE COMPOSITES IN ROTATIONAL MOLDING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

In this study, the antioxidant properties of black tea wastes as a filler of polyethylene composites were investigated. An extensive analysis was carried out to evaluate the possibility of stabilization the polyethylene composite. The used matrix was biobased low-density polyethylene (LDPE SEB 853 I'm Green[®]). The filler was introduced in 1, 2, 5, and 10 wt% in the extrusion process. First, the antioxidant properties of the natural filler were investigated using UV-Vis assays. To obtain thermal properties as the temperature of the beginning of degradation, we conducted a thermogravimetric analysis of composites in an inert and oxidative atmosphere. The composites were also evaluated in terms of their thermal properties in the presence of oxygen by OIT (oxygen induction time) determination to confirm stabilization effects. Adding 10 wt% of black tea waste increases OIT nearly 36 times compared to the unmodified polymer. Prepared composites have also been tested after accelerated aging under thermo-oxidative conditions to determine the carbonyl index in the FTIR test. Then, a thoroughly investigated material was cryogenically milled to a fine powder for rotational molding purpose. The rotomolded samples were subjected to the Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy; it appears that the addition of 10 wt% black tea waste prevents the formation of carbonyl compounds in polyethylene.

1. Introduction

Polyethylene is highly susceptible to thermal oxidation. The presence of oxygen at elevated temperatures causes chain scission, leading to the degradation of the material. This process starts with forming free radicals in the initiation mechanism, and then in the next step, the peroxy radicals are formed due to the propagation mechanism [1].

Rotational molding is the most dynamically developing technology for forming thin-walled, large-size products. It enables the manufacturing of tanks and containers from thermoplastic polymers, especially polyethylene, in one operation. It involves heating the polymer powder in a mold rotating in two axes, covering the entire internal surface of the mold in the polymer sintering process, followed by densification, cooling of the material, and demolding of the ready-to-use product [2]. Due to the polymer's low thermal conductivity and the process's nature in which no technological procedures are used in its initial phase to accelerate the first sintering phase, the polymer is subjected to long-term exposure to high temperatures in oxidizing conditions. This makes rotational molding one of the most material-demanding technologies for processing thermoplastics, generating the need to stabilize the molded polymer [3].

Antioxidants are added to prevent this degradation. The commercially available materials have artificial stabilizers, with the most commonly used pentaerythritol tetrakis(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyhydrocinnamate) known commercially as Irganox 1010. The use of stabilizers allows not only the manufacturing of a product free of defects and good quality but also extends the life of the molded parts by limiting the amount of free radicals in their structure. As an effect, polymeric products are less vulnerable to deterioration of mechanical properties due to degradation of their macromolecular structure during processing and long-term exposure to environmental conditions [4,5]. Furthermore, the growing ecological awareness of society leads not only to the development of new sustainable technologies and materials but also allows to determine humans' long-term ecological negative impact on the environment. Currently considered a threat, "microplastics" are one of the actual research topics on the effects of synthetic materials on the environment [6,7]. However, the latest studies indicates that the presence of migrating modifiers from polymers to the environment is an increasingly severe problem. Several studies have proved the migration of stabilizers directly to foods and the environment [8–10].

The possible way to reduce potential environmental hazards related to synthetic antioxidants is to utilize compounds naturally occurring in fruits, herbs, and vegetables [11]. Phenolic compounds like quercetin [12,13], gallic acid [14], curcumin [15], and α -Tocopherol [13] are commonly used to stabilize polyethylene. The next group of compounds are extracts from plants like rosemary [16,17], oregano, green tea, and grapefruit seeds [18] for food packaging. The newest trend is to incorporate ground plant parts as fillers, especially waste like spent coffee grounds, cocoa husk [19], black tea waste [20], and agro wastes [21].

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the production process and assessment of the properties of polyethylene composites filled with black tea waste.

Research shows that the addition of extracted active compounds alone and the addition of fragmented plant parts used as active fillers can produce beneficial stabilization effects. The low-molecular-weight compounds rich in flavonoids and polyphenols contained in them migrate to the polymer matrix, increasing the oxidation resistance of polymers [22–24]. Due to biomass diversification, this is an uncontrolled process and, therefore, requires further detailed research. It should be emphasized that while individual plants have been described as potential active fillers, the impact of pre-processing and final melt-mixing processes on their effectiveness is still undescribed.

This study aims to provide a comprehensive summary of preliminary research on using black tea waste (BTW) as a functional filler with antioxidant properties in polyethylene composites formed in the rotational molding process. As part of the experimental work, composites were produced in the extrusion process and characterized for changes in oxidation stability in the molten state by determination of oxygen induction time (OIT) and those caused by thermal aging (90 °C for 15 days). Then, these materials were processed in a laboratory and up-scalable [25] uniaxial rotational molding process to assess the effectiveness of the BTW impact on changes in the chemical structure and mechanical properties of biobased polyethylene. A flowchart showing a comprehensive approach to problem description is shown in Figure 1.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and sample preparation

The matrix for manufacturing the composites is biobased low-density polyethylene SEB 853 I'm Green® Braskem. The used waste filler is black tea dust collected by a tea packaging and distribution company (Poland). The filler was introduced into the polyethylene matrix in 1, 2, 5, and 10 wt%.

Composite materials were mixed in melt state using a twin-screw extruder, a ZAMAK EH16.2D. Parameters in this process are 100 rpm of the rotational speed of screws and 120 °C set as the highest temperature. To better homogenize the material second extrusion was performed at the same temperature set but higher rotational speed of screws (250 rpm). LDPE matrix as well as black tea waste (BTW), were dried before extrusion for 12 h at 60 °C. Samples prepared for evaluation properties after the thermo-oxidation aging were compression molded with a Remiplast hydraulic press; the temperature was set at 130 °C, and the highest pressure during forming was 18 MPa. The heating step lasted 2 min, followed by cooling in forced airflow for 4 min. Thermo-oxidation was established to investigate the free radical scavenging ability of the rich-in-active-compounds filler. This process was held in an air-circulating oven for 15 days at 100°C.

Materials used for rotational molding must be in a powder form; therefore, pelleted material was ground using a centrifugal mill Retsch ZM 200 with a 500 µm sieve, operating at 6,000 rpm. To prevent material from overheating, dry ice was added during grinding. The rotational molding was performed using a uniaxial rotomolding machine Rotorocket by 493K (Fig.1). Heating process continued until the temperature inside the mold reached 200 °C. After that, the mold was cooled in a forced airflow. The rotational speed of the mold was 10 rpm.

2.2. Methods

To analyze the possible stabilization effect of the fillers rich in antioxidants, the oxygen induction time (OIT) method was established. This method is based on differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) in the presence of oxygen. For each extruded and compression-molded material, 5 mg samples were taken and placed in aluminum crucibles with pierced lids. In the first method section, the temperature increases at a rate of 20 °C/min to finally reach 190 °C, then the isothermal phase for 5 min, it takes place in an atmosphere of nitrogen. This is followed by switching the atmosphere to oxygen and recording the time after which oxidation of the material occurs. This test was performed using the Netzsch 204 F1 Phoenix instrument in a triplicate.

The antioxidant activity of composites can be evaluated using the procedure proposed by Rojas-Lema et al. [26]. To do this, the 63 µM solution of DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) in methanol was prepared. The 100 mg samples were cut off from each composite material and immersed with 5 ml of prepared solution, which was contained in dark glass flasks for 2, 24, 48, and 96 h. Subsequently, the solution after each of that time was subjected to UV-vis spectroscopy at UV wavelength of 517 nm. The

control vials contain only the DPPH solution in dark glass to protect it from UV light. This analysis aims to calculate inhibition (IC), determining the percentage of radical scavenging ability as follows:

$$IC = \frac{A_{control} - A_{sample}}{A_{control}} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where $A_{control}$ – absorbance of DPPH solution at 517 nm, A_{sample} – absorbance of the sample at 517 nm. All measurements were performed using Spectrophotometer UV-VIS UviLine 9400.

Samples submitted to thermal oxidation and the one formed in rotational molding were evaluated using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Measurements were performed using the Jasco FT/IR-4600 apparatus with a resolution 4 cm^{-1} and 64 scans in a wavenumber range of $4000 - 400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Recorded spectra and their absorbance in the range $1800 - 1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating carbonyl group ($A_{C=O}$) and absorbance of a methylene group ($A_0 - 1500 \text{ to } 1420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) helped to calculate carbonyl index - CI (2). This is a commonly used indicator to evaluate oxidation levels.

$$CI = \frac{A_{C=O}}{A_0} \quad (2)$$

Thermo-oxidation and rotational molding caused changes in the color of initially obtained composites. To determine the influence of high-temperature and processing conditions on color, the total color change (ΔE) was calculated (3). Color measurements were performed in CIELab color space to carry out this analysis. The apparatus used in this evaluation is NR145 Precision Colorimetry 3nh supplied with the light source D65, the measuring aperture is $\Phi 8\text{mm}$, and the viewing geometry $45^\circ/0^\circ$.

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{\Delta L^2 + \Delta a^2 + \Delta b^2} \quad (3)$$

3. Results and discussion

Increasing filler content has a positive impact on the stabilization of LDPE composites. Adding black tea waste gradually increases OIT with the rising filler concentration in the composite structure. The same phenomenon was observed in the reduction of absorbance of the DPPH solution after soaking in it the LDPE composites. Increasing immersion time results in increased inhibition. This proved the migration of low molecular polyphenolic compounds from fillers dispersed in a composite structure with the highest effectiveness for samples with 5 and 10 wt% BTW.

Figure 2. Antioxidant properties of the samples expressed as oxygen induction time (a) and DPPH inhibition (b).

As proven in the previously mentioned study, the phenomenal antioxidant properties of black tea waste have been tested in processing conditions and during accelerated aging. Rotational molding is a process where the material is exposed to elevated temperatures for a long time. The oxidation level measured as carbonyl index (CI) is much higher in rotomolded samples than for aged samples for 15 days at 90°C . Rotational molding conditions caused extensive oxidation of the polyethylene; however, the addition of 10 wt% of black tea waste prevents complete chain scission reactions, leading to oxidation and material degradation. Increasing the amount of filler slightly decreased the carbonyl index compared to neat

LDPE. On the other hand, keeping the material for 15 days at 90 °C did not cause extensive oxidation; only neat LDPE exhibits oxidation. Composite samples were "self-stabilized" from the effects of elevated temperatures in an oxidizing atmosphere by indirectly introducing a filler with antioxidant properties. Thermal oxidation and rotational molding resulted in the discoloration of used materials compared to untreated compression molded samples. Higher total color change was noted for rotomolded samples. Specimens with a lower filler content exhibit higher discoloration due to the higher oxidation level. Thermally oxidized materials have the highest discoloration for 2% BTW; the same effect was confirmed for rotomolded samples, but the color change coefficient for rotomolded material is almost five times higher.

Figure 3. Properties after thermal oxidation and uniaxial rotational molding.

4. Conclusions

An analysis of carbonyl index values confirmed the demanding processing conditions of rotational molding technology. A comparison of this index between rotomolded and thermally oxidized samples shows a considerable difference. This phenomenon confirms the importance of carefully selecting stabilizers for polyethylene in the case of rotational molding technology. Using 10 wt% of BTW avoided oxidation of the material; it is also a sample with the highest oxidation induction time. It can be concluded that the filler selected for this study can serve as a sustainable stabilizer of polyethylene in thermal aging conditions in all its concentrations. Only the previously mentioned material with 10% BTW reveals sufficient antioxidant efficiency in the rotational molding conditions.

Data availability statement

The data is deposited in an open repository database and will be provided after contacting the corresponding author.

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